

HØGENHAVEN, J. — *The Cave 3 Copper Scroll: A Symbolic Journey*. (Studies on the Texts of the Desert of Judah, 132). Brill Academic Publishers, Leiden-Boston, 2020. (24 cm, X, 267). ISBN 978-90-04-42855-3. ISSN 0169-9962. € 116,-.

Ever since its discovery in 1952, the Copper Scroll (3Q15) has been a point of fascination due to its medium as well as the preserved text—a supposed account of hidden treasures. In part the product of stays at École Biblique in Jerusalem, this monograph explores this “most mysterious” of texts within the Qumran corpus. Set against the backdrop of the scholarly debate regarding the nature of the Copper Scroll, Jesper Høgenhaven undertakes a fresh examination of the Copper Scroll as a literary text. For Høgenhaven, the document was “designed by its author to convey specific images to the reader” employing a specifically chosen format and style, namely that of instructions for retrieving hidden treasures (p. 1). Høgenhaven reads the Copper Scroll within a specific historical and literary context, understanding the text as a response to the concerns within Jewish Palestine in the first century CE and as a text located within the Qumran corpus and the wider landscape of ancient Jewish literature.

After a brief introduction outlining the goals and trajectory of the study, *Chapter 1 Legend or History: A Brief History of Scholarship* provides the reader with an extensive overview of the history of scholarship of the Copper Scroll from its discovery in 1952 to the present. Høgenhaven explores the discovery of the scroll, the publication of the text including J. T. Milik’s *editio princeps* in DJD 3 (1962) and Émile

Puech’s important 2006 text edition, as well as the discussions surrounding the provenance and linguistic characteristics of the scroll. Important for his proposal, Høgenhaven closely traces the contours of scholarly debate concerning the question of whether the Copper Scroll reflects an “authentic” record or a work of literary fiction regarding the hidden treasure described in the scroll. While admitting that definitive answers are beyond reach, Høgenhaven closes the chapter with a consideration of the key questions that will guide his study, most significantly, questions regarding the function and purpose of the Copper Scroll.

In *Chapter 2 A Walk on the Wild Side: A Suggestive Reading of 3Q15*, Høgenhaven undertakes a literary reading of the Copper Scroll, reading the instructive voice sequentially guiding the addressee through a geographic landscape of places, monuments, and hidden treasure. Høgenhaven concludes that the distribution of the geographic locations lends to reading the Copper Scroll as an itinerary of sorts—prescribing the movements of the addressee (and the implied reader) on a symbolic journey through the Palestinian landscape. Additionally, Høgenhaven proposes a “provisory division” of the text seeing four main literary divisions: the first section as a *prologue* beginning in the Valley of Anchor and prefiguring the addressee’s journey to Jerusalem (1:1–4:2), a second section as an *interlude* directing the addressee around Secacah towards the Kidron Valley (4:13–8:3), a third and *main section* chronicling the long journey of the addressee up the Kidron Valley to Jerusalem, and most significantly for Høgenhaven the tomb of Zadok (8:4–12:3), and a fourth section consisting of a brief *epilogue* in which the addressee is directed to three locations in the North and to the final destination in Kohlit (12:4–13). Significant for Høgenhaven is the general impression offered by the images presented along the journey, namely that of the decay and desolation of the land on the one hand, a glimmer of the consolation of hope and restoration on the other. This leads directly into *Chapter 3 A Map of Meanings: Places and Items in the Copper Scroll* and the exploration of the potential symbolism that lies behind the presented images.

Engaging the work of Christopher Tilley’s work on landscape theory,¹⁾ specifically that “landscape” embodies both an experienced location as well as an imagined one continually shaped by humans, Høgenhaven maps the locations and place names, the distribution of hidden valuables, and the location of the hiding places into a larger symbolic schema. Høgenhaven arrives a several conclusions. *First*, the symbolic value displayed by the mapping of textual characteristics further supports his proposal that the Copper Scroll can be meaningfully read as a literary text. *Second*, the symbolism evoked by the textual characteristics is meaningfully derived from past traditions, while at the same time upholding a critique of the present and a hope of restoration in the future. The locations and place names listed in the Copper Scroll evoke Israel’s past literary traditions, particularly those attached to the wilderness wanderings and the conquest of the Promised Land. For Høgenhaven, the lack of explicit mention of Jerusalem coupled with the hiding of a considerable number of sacred objects associated with the Temple speak symbolically to the city and Temple as not functioning properly. On the other hand, the location of the hiding of

¹⁾ Christopher Tilley, *A Phenomenology of Landscape: Place, Paths and Monuments* (Oxford: Berg, 1994).

many of these objects, namely that of “the tomb of Zadok” can be construed as symbolically pointing to an alternative sanctuary and a future restoration. The larger desolate and ruined landscape, signified by abandoned buildings, architectural remains and water installations, as well as frequently cited subterranean hiding places, speaks to the present-day condition of God’s people. Significant for Høgenhaven is the final cache of treasure, a duplicate copy of the text itself, which not only marks the end of the addressee’s journey but also reflects its zenith, the acquisition of wisdom and knowledge in continuity with past tradition. The instructive voice, therefore, leads the addressee on a symbolic journey through the echoes of Israel’s past traditions into a present marked by desolation and decay.

Chapter 4 What is Real? The Copper Scroll as Material Artefact returns to questions concerning the materiality of the Copper Scroll as a framework for assessing the debate between its “authentic” or “fictitious” nature. The chapter begins with an exploration of the material status and character of the Copper Scroll including the matters of provenance, paleographic analysis, dating, philological analysis, material considerations, and whether the genre description of the Copper Scroll as “list” or “catalogue” is heuristically useful. On the question of the latter, Høgenhaven suggests that the notion of “list” should be understood as an expression of “construction type” rather than a genre designation leading to assumptions of a non-literary text. Høgenhaven discusses the arguments for and against the authenticity of the deposits, focusing on the work of Al Wolters for the former and Hanan Eshel/Zeev Safrai and Leslaw Morawiecki for the latter.²⁾ For Høgenhaven, a dichotomy of “authentic” or “fictional” is wholly inadequate for understanding the Copper Scroll, rather a more nuanced approach is required. Suggesting that some of the deposits may have been real in a historical sense while others were what might be considered legendary, Høgenhaven concludes the Copper Scroll is grounded in the historical realities and turmoil of mid-first century CE Jewish Palestine and “represents an attempt of describing all the hidden treasures, past and present, of a desolate Holy Land awaiting its final redemption” (p. 188).

The final chapter, *Chapter 5 What We Were Told: Traditional and Literary Contexts for the Copper Scroll*, serves to place the Copper Scroll within the larger landscape of literary tradition concerned with hidden treasure as well as its potential connections with the themes and concerns expressed within the Qumran corpus. Høgenhaven begins with an examination of various literary traditions which have been thought analogous to the Copper Scroll: the Jewish *Massekhet Kelim* and the Arabic *The Book of the Treasured Pearls*, both suggested by Milik in his *editio princeps*; inventory lists, such as an inscribed ossuary lid from Bethphage, the Aramaic *Megillat Ta’anit*, and the temple inventory from the Isle of Delos, as suggested by Michael Wise; and the *Lindian Chronicle* as suggested by Steven Weitzman.³⁾ Noting the

relevant similarities and dissimilarities with the Copper Scroll, Høgenhaven advances the *Lindian Chronicle* as offering the closest analogy given the structure and composition of entries as well as the explicit links to prominent places and people of past traditions. Høgenhaven sees further connections with texts which include the fate of First Temple sacred objects, texts such as 2 Maccabees, *Vitae prophetarum*, and Second Baruch, all of which significantly feature eschatological expectations of restoration. Significantly, Høgenhaven makes an argument that even though the Copper Scroll does not contain any explicit Qumran “sectarian” language it does have significant points of contact with other writings within the Qumran corpus. The image of a land that is desolate and in decay as well as a Temple that is non-functioning and disqualified it quite compatible with other writings from Qumran. That the hiding place of the Temple sacred objects is the tomb of Zadok provides another point of contact given the importance of Zadok at Qumran. The notion of a renewed Temple, albeit not made explicit in the Copper Scroll, shows affinity with the Temple Scroll and the Aramaic New Jerusalem text (4Q544). Finally, the motif of desolation and destruction found in the Copper Scroll posits intriguing connections with compositions such as Tanhumim (4Q176) and Apocryphal Lamentations A and B (4Q179 and 4Q501).

This monograph represents the fruition of Høgenhaven’s thinking on the subject undertaken in his earlier work (2009 and 2015) and aptly stands alongside previous studies on the Copper Scroll (Brooke/Davies in 2002, Brizemeure, Lacoudre, Puech in 2006, and Puech in 2015) as an essential treatment on the subject. Høgenhaven’s reading of the Copper Scroll as a literary text is innovative and convincing, adding a fresh contribution to the scholarly discourse surrounding the nature and function of the Copper Scroll. Particularly intriguing is his discussion regarding the ideological affinities between the Copper Scroll and other compositions within the Qumran corpus derived from a literary reading. To my mind, this line of inquiry is ripe for broader investigation. This monograph is to be highly commended not only regarding its generous engagement with previous scholarship and careful reading of the Copper Scroll, but also for providing an illuminating treatment of a text which has received muted attention.

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19 June 2021

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²⁾ See Al Wolters, “Apocalyptic and the Copper Scroll,” *JNES* 49 (1990): 145–54; Hanan Eshel and Zeev Safrai, “אלו אוצרות נרשמו במגילת”, *Cathedra* 103 (2007), 7–20; and Leslaw Morawiecki, “The Copper Scroll Treasure: A Fantasy or Stock Inventory?” *QC* 4 (1994): 169–74.

³⁾ See Michael O. Wise, “David J. Wilmot and the Copper Scroll” in *Copper Scroll Studies*, eds. George J. Brooke and Philip Davies, *JSJSup* 40 (Sheffield: Sheffield Academic Press), 291–310 and Steven P. Weitzman, “Absent but Accounted For: A New Approach to the Copper Scroll,” *HTR* 108 (2015): 423–47.